

Call: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06
Topic: HORIZON-HLTH-2021-TOOL-06-03
Funding Scheme: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions (RIA)

Grant Agreement no: 101057062

AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Deliverable No. 4.5

1st Report of the Ethics Advisory Board

Contractual Submission Date: 29/02/2024

Actual Submission Date: 19/04/2024

Responsible partner: P5 i~HD

**Funded by
the European Union**

Grant agreement no.	101057062
Project full title	AIDAVA - AI powered Data Curation & Publishing Virtual Assistant

Deliverable number	D4.5
Deliverable title	1st Report of the Ethics Advisory Board
Type ¹	Report
Dissemination level ²	PU
Work package number	4
Work package leader	P5 i~HD
Author(s)	Internal: Nathan Lea, Isabelle de Zegher, Dipak Kalra External Experts: Don Willison, Brendan Barnes, Julie Power, Peter Singleton,
Keywords	Ethics, Advisory, Regulatory Compliance, Oversight, Risk Management, Transparency, Accountability

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The work of MID received funding by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SBFI), subvention contract 22.00093, REF-1131-52104.

Supported by a licence waiver from SNOMED International from a period of 2 years (2024 – 2025), on condition that SNOMED CT is not used and/or deployed commercially.

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.5	29/02/2024	First draft written by Nathan Lea for dissemination, and input from internal and external co-authors
V1.0	20/03/2024	Submission Draft Candidate after EAB feedback, pending final EAB approval
V1.1	14/04/2024	EAB Approved Version

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Definitions

The definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [\[ref\]](#).

Executive Summary

This Deliverable D4.5 provides the first report of AIDAVA's Ethics Advisory Board of experts (EAB) . It summarises the main activities of the EAB and provides details of current and next steps in ethics oversight of AIDAVA.

D4.5 provides details of the establishment of the EAB, its operation, membership, key points of focus and concludes with next steps. Key points of focus include considerations of bias in the recruitments of study participants and the digital divide, whether study participants and the Patient Consultants are representative of the patient population in terms of socio-demographics, whether the introduction of an AIDAVA solution places undue burden on patient participants and Curators within health care providers who are identified by AIDAVA as offering support.

Annexes to this report include the Terms of Reference.

AIDAVA faces and is addressing challenges posed by new regulation and technology use, unexplored patient involvement paradigms and forthcoming regulations. The need for a representative EAB including as many stakeholders views and expertise as possible is clear. The EAB has therefore been formed and is keen to commence work on reviewing AIDAVA.

The EAB will meet as outlined in this report and will engage with AIDAVA in terms of the ongoing assessments and reviews as the solutions are developed and trialled. Further learning will be gleaned from attendance at the pilot assessments in May in Maastricht, and ongoing consideration and oversight as AIDAVA develops. Further liaison with the project partners and the SAB will enhance and enrich the understanding and the addressing of the challenges that AIDAVA faces.

1 Introduction

This Deliverable D4.5 provides the first report of AIDAVA's Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) of experts. It has been drafted in partnership between the external experts and AIDAVA's internal team members from WP1 and WP4. It provides a summary of the main activities since the EAB was established in September 2023 and discusses its constitution, activities and key points of focus.

Details of the EAB including its recruitment, membership, operation and future plans in terms of immediate and longer term next steps are also covered. The EAB have agreed broad focus points for their review and will attend a Face to Face meeting workshop in Maastricht to be held in May so that they can better understand the proposed operation of the AIDAVA Platform and the test run of the trial. These focus points and the attendance at the workshop are described in more details. D4.5 concludes with a consideration of the first year of activity and proposed immediate and long term next steps for the EAB and its oversight of AIDAVA.

The Running Minutes of the EAB are available on request. The Terms of Reference (ToR) are provided in Annex 5.2.

2 Description of Activities

This section describes the activities of the EAB from recruitment to meeting and initial operation. It provides a basis for the Results of the EAB deliberations described in Section 3.

2.1 Recruitment

In early 2023 AIDAVA partners commenced recruitment of a panel of experts to independently oversee and advise on the data protection, security, ethics and integrity of the project. This was to fulfil the requirements and commitments outlined in the AIDAVA Grant Agreement and wider requirements of the funders. The appointment of an EAB is critical for ensuring that AIDAVA can meet its regulatory and wider ethical compliance when handling sensitive data and engaging with human participants.

WP4 worked closely with WP1 to identify and select appropriate candidates for the EAB. This list of candidates was approved by the AIDAVA Steering Committee in February 2023. The recruitment letters were sent in March 2023 and all invited experts save for one replied and accepted.

On acceptance of the invitation the EAB was formally appointed and its first meeting was held in September 2023.

The Deliverable notes the involvement of Birgit Bauer as the Patient Representative for the EAB. Due to other pressing commitments Birgit Bauer had to stand down as an EAB member. She has been Replaced by Julie Power. AIDAVA expressed their gratitude for Birgit's time and input as described below.

The full EAB Membership is therefore as follows:

External members	Role and Background
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Birgit Bauer	Patient Representative and Project Coordinator of Data Saves Lives Germany. (Stood down March 2024)
Brendan Barnes	Regulatory Expert and Former Privacy Officer for EFPIA (retired)
Julie Power	Patient Representative - Patient Contact and Policy Officer for Vasculitis Ireland Awareness (commencing March 2024)
Peter Singleton	Regulatory Expert and Director Cambridge Health Informatics
Don Willison	Chair, Public Health and Governance Expert, Faculty Member, University of Toronto
Sofia Palmieri (observer)	Observer and PhD Candidate.
Internal Members	
Dipak Kalra	WP4 Lead
Nathan Lea	Task 4.1 Lead
Isabelle de Zegher	Clinical Lead and co-coordinator
Kerli Norak	WP1 Lead
Gabrijela Radic	Project management Office

2.2 Meetings and Operation

The initial meeting for AIDAVA was held on 29th September 2023 and there have since been 2 additional meetings with the whole EAB. One was a follow up to the 29th September 2023 held on 6th December 2023, and another has been held recently on 18th March 2024.

After the Meeting held on 6th December 2023 the EAB unanimously appointed Don Willison as Chair of the EAB. Don Willison subsequently agreed to hold brief fortnightly meetings with Task 4.1 Lead Nathan Lea to oversee and manage the operation of the EAB, including scheduling meetings and developing agenda items, as well as any additional activities that may be required.

The EAB has agreed that it will look to meet quarterly with at least one face-to-face meeting per annum. They will also try to coincide this with AIDAVA General Assembly meetings where possible so that they can observe their operation. The first face-to-face meeting is likely to be at the App Design Workshop to be held in Maastricht in May 2024 with an additional face to face at the General Assembly in October.. The EAB Members will attend and participate in the May workshop as observers and will hold a parallel EAB face to face meeting whilst they are in attendance. In the October Workshop they will meet with the Sustainability Advisory Board so that each board can learn more about their operation and how they might work with one another.

From an operational perspective, Don Willison as Chair and Nathan Lea as T4.1 lead a meeting fortnightly to oversee and manage any developments for the EAB and continue to address the ongoing business. The running minutes of the meetings are available on request as specified in Annex 7.1..

3 Activities and Outputs Discussion

To date the EAB has been able to establish the particulars of its operation and start to identify key points of focus that represent ethical and regulatory challenges for AIDAVA.. The outcomes of the meetings have been:

- draft Terms of Reference that will be ratified after the initial face to face meeting in Maastricht (where the EAB will be able to observe the tool and consider their key points of focus);
- completion of Non Disclosure Agreements (NDA) for the EAB members to sign so that EAB members and the integrity of the project can be protected;
- establishment of a modus operandi for the EAB; and
- Identification of key points of focus for the EAB, based on ethical and regulatory challenges AIDAVA investigators have identified. These are listed in section 3.1.

The Running Minutes of the EAB are available on request.

3.1 Key Points of Focus for the EAB

There are two areas that AIDAVA is addressing.

The first is at the patients' level - to support them in controlling, integrating and cleaning their health data from multiple sources (including their own apps and monitoring systems) for their own benefit. The Health Data Intermediary (HDI) role is a new paradigm for this and will need further consideration.

The second - stemming from the first one - is at a level of care to assist frontline healthcare providers in addressing more effectively the care needs of their patients using the most comprehensive collection of data available.

In assessing AIDAVA and its activities, the EAB has started by considering the roles of the different stakeholders: patients, curators, HDI, clinical care teams amongst others. Some roles identified by AIDAVA are novel - including that of the HDI, that of the Curator and that of the Patient Consultants.

3.1.1 Patient and Citizen voices must be maximised

For the **Patient Consultants**, the immediate points of focus involve the representation of the patient community overall. The EAB have taken an interest in how the Consultants have been recruited and how AIDAVA can identify, mitigate against and manage bias in their selection, as well as the patient participants. The EAB appreciates the strategy that has been put in place by AIDAVA in recruiting patients and will consider this and how they may be able to assist in more detail after observing the pilot of the evaluation in Maastricht in May.

The system will be assessed by **Site Patients** within each evaluation site. Considerations for burden on these Site Patients and questions around biases or prejudice are forming part of the EAB's areas of identified focus and priority, specifically around the level of technical ability that may be required for using the AIDAVA solutions and the subsequent risk of exacerbating the digital divide. Solutions to

address this are therefore a priority. The digital literacy questionnaire that AIDAVA has designed is a means to tackle this challenge. It is available under Section 10.3 of the Study Protocol. The EAB welcomed the inclusion of the questionnaire and asked about whether the participant recruitment to evaluate AIDAVA may itself deter those who are not tech confident prior to scaling up the deployment of the solutions to a wider audience who may not be able to engage as readily and thereafter be left out.

Another area that the EAB may need to consider relates to the capacity of the AIDAVA pilot, which is necessarily focused on specific conditions, to address the full complexity of the patient's sense of their condition. This would involve the EAB developing a better understanding of the patient journey throughout the project - as described in the schedule of activities of the Study Protocol - and potentially the need for them to better exercise choice at different points. The EAB will also consider the position after the local Research Ethics Committees have taken a view on this matter and any challenges the Research Ethics Committees may raise around participant burden, and will offer support on how to address any challenges that may arise.

Overall the EAB members are keen to discover approaches to ensure that the patient voice and that of the wider citizenry is heard in the design, development, testing and potential deployment of the AIDAVA solution. This is in parallel with wider considerations and points of focus, in particular the implications of approaching a wider cohort of patients and citizens outside of the AIDAVA assessment context to understand their technical proficiency, needs and expectations around the AIDAVA solution.

3.1.2 Role & responsibilities of the Curator

From the perspective of the Curator the EAB has started to consider the implications for this new role. The main points of concern are around the availability of and readiness for Curators to assist patients with the work of managing their health records. Does this place an undue burden on the Curators and the patients themselves? The EAB wishes to understand this aspect better and pursue it moving forward. The current types of Curator are as follows:

- Curator = the patient - or their consented delegate - at their level of health and digital literacy (levels range from 1 to 10). Note: An expert data scientist or expert physician can be a patient.
Incentive: high quality personal data for better care
- Expert curator = dedicated and trained people with various levels of health and digital literacy (expected to have a high level of digital literacy and preferably a high level of health literacy). During the prototype evaluation, the expert curator can be hospital staff (nurse, junior clinicians, medical secretary).
Incentive: part of regular work activities
- Community curator (Long term vision, to be developed) = any citizen with some level of health and digital literacy, trained to the issue of data interoperability to increase their level of health and digital literacy (at least at the same level as an expert curator), ready to support multiple patients. Could be a family member, a retired health professional etc.
Incentive: common good, support to loved ones, paid for service.

The EAB will enhance their understanding of these kinds of Curator roles and their implications. This question had already been raised by the Sustainability Advisory Board (SAB). The EAB have expressed interest in liaising with the SAB and such liaison will likely promote shared understanding for independent experts for the newer concepts AIDAVA has started to introduce.

3.1.3 Data quality

The EAB also wishes to ensure there is an examination of the quality of the data being used to train the different algorithms used as curation tools, and the quality of data included in the personal knowledge graphs. They have identified a need to assure that this will not undermine the integrity of the AIDAVA solution and it will require careful consideration taking into account the activities of Task 4.2 on data quality, Task 4.3 on annotations, Task 5.1 on building NLP models and Task 5.2 on building novel curation tools.

These are the key points of focus that the EAB have agreed initially are points of interest. They will await the Maastricht workshop - during which a Dry Run evaluation will take place with Patient Consultants and representatives from the different sites - to further develop and enhance these areas of consideration when they observe the pilot.

The EAB have also considered how they might assess these areas, discussed in the next section.

3.2 EAB Oversight and Assessment

In considering the key areas of focus, the EAB has also considered how these might be reviewed and assessed. In addition to observing the Dry Run workshop and engaging directly with AIDAVA team members, the EAB will consider the implications of adherence to not only current and recent regulations (like the Data Governance Act) but also forthcoming regulations and how they might be addressed. For example the forthcoming AI Act makes provision for addressing bias in data, its quality, transparency with users and data subjects as well as societal impacts and implications in context - including whether an AI driven intervention will replace human intervention and interaction. The EHDS has implications around the quality and interoperability of data and its sources and this will have implications for AIDAVA. The EAB will continue to keep abreast of these areas, and may be informed by the use of the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI.

In parallel with this the EU Commission produced the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) and an online Toolkit for evaluating similar aspects to those covered by the AI Act as well as the focus points for the EAB. The EAB therefore agreed to consider using this as a tool to review the points to be clarified with the consortium. The EAB has identified the need to reconcile the ALTAI Toolkit particulars with that of other areas of regulatory compliance, including GDPR, so that other regulatory considerations can be included. This is an important point for the EAB to agree moving forward - that ALTAI focuses on AI but the challenges identified for AIDAVA from the ethical and compliance perspectives are not necessarily specific to AI - rather they are steeped in known challenges around bias and engagement.

4 Conclusion

AIDAVA as a project is exploring newer pathways as part of citizen empowerment when it comes to the management of their own data to support their own health and care administration in partnership with their health care professional teams and carers. It is partnering with Health Data Intermediaries to explore how this new service paradigm can best support citizen empowerment and the furtherance of health data driven innovation.

AIDAVA is doing this using new technology including AI systems and machine learning amidst the preparation of near finalisation of new legislation around AI and the management of health data through the EHDS. The ethical and regulatory needs and challenges are as a result complex and mostly as of yet unexplored. This situation therefore requires more than ever the oversight of an EAB that is representative of the ehealth data innovation space and its stakeholders.

The EAB has therefore been formed and is keen to commence work on reviewing AIDAVA. It will meet as outlined in this report and will engage with AIDAVA in terms of the ongoing assessments and reviews as the solutions are developed and trialled. Further learning will be gleaned from attendance at the Dry Run workshop in May in Maastricht, and ongoing consideration and oversight as AIDAVA develops. Further liaison with the project partners and the SAB will enhance and enrich the understanding and the addressing of the challenges that AIDAVA faces.

5 Annexes

5.1 EAB Running Minutes

Available on request.

5.2 Terms of Reference: Mission & responsibility of the Ethics Advisory Board

Mission

The mission of the Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) is to promote a strong ethical foundation throughout the project.

Composition & operations

The EAB will appoint approximately five independent experts, including ethics experts, data protection experts; at least one of whom would be a lawyer in health data protection and at least one of whom will be an expert in the ethics of AI. One of the members will be a patient representative. Partner i~HD (Prof Dipak Karla) and Task 4.1 will convene and support this group, but it will be chaired by one of the external experts.

The EAB will meet every 3 months: three times per year through teleconferences (1.5 hour meetings) and once a year joining the life General Assembly (full day meeting). The project is expected to last for 4 years.

Before each meeting, EAB members will be provided with an update of the project and a set of key topics to discuss and relevant documentation, in support of the topics.

EAB's advice will be reported in official deliverables of the project. Meetings and reporting will be supported by Partner i~HD who is also leading Work Package 4 Task 4.1 on the ELSI aspects of AIDAVA and acting as secretariat of the EAB. A yearly deliverable comprising the annual report of the EAB will be produced.

EAB Members will sign a Non Disclosure Agreement the template for which is available here: [\[ref\]](#).

Key areas of focus

The EAB will address the following key areas:

- To assess and advise on the regulatory compliance in terms of data protection, research governance and ethical considerations;
- To ensure that the stakeholders with an interest in AIDAVA – specifically patients, the wider public, clinicians, AI and software developers, regulators, researchers and commissioners – are well represented in terms of the project mission;
- To consider key ethical challenges – including, but not limited to, the impacts from a societal perspective of the Data Governance Act including greater control and responsibility for record keeping and interactions with their clinical teams;
- To provide AIDAVA partners support and guidance for publications and Deliverables on request where there is a timely request for comments and feedback (e.g. three weeks' notice).
- To review all the data protection and information security instruments that are developed to enable compliance with data protection and ethical approvals, and will monitor the activities of the project.

Budget

Travel budget - and daily allowance of 600 EUR (whenever needed - assuming 4 out of the group) - will be covered by the project.

Assume 5 experts, assume 4 out of 5 need to be paid, assume one cannot be paid as in industry
Assume the following fees per paid expert

	per unit	unit per year	cost per year	cost for project
Full day face to face meeting (one per year - 4 across project)	€ 600	4	€ 2,400	€ 9,600
Half day virtual meeting (one per year - 4 across project or shorter virtual meetings with greater frequency as needed)	€ 300	4	€ 1,200	€ 4,800
Reading time prior to each meeting (key deliverables, briefing documents) - 2 times per year	€ 150	8	€ 1,200	€ 4,800
Travel for all 5 experts per face to face meeting, (once per year)	€ 775	5	€ 3,875	€ 15,500
			€ 8,675	€ 34,700

Name of board members

External members	Organisation	Email
Brendan Barnes	EFPIA Privacy Officer (Retired)	brendan1957@gmail.com
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Peter Singleton	Cambridge Health Informatics	peter.singleton@chi-group.com
Don Willison	University of Toronto	don.willison@utoronto.ca
Sofia Palmieri (observer)		PhD linked to IHD
Internal Members		
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